

METAPHORICAL FEATURES IN THE CREATION OF THE TEXTURE

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Abstract: metaphor is a figure of speech, a rhetorical effect that means one thing by directly mentioning the other. It is possible to identify explicit (or implicit) or hidden similarities between two ideas. Metaphor is often compared to other types of figurative language, such as antithesis, hyperbole, metonymy and comparison.

Key words: metaphor, texture, language, linguists, linguistic theories, metaphorical language activates, concepts, definitions, metaphoric extension, vocabulary, meaning

One of the tools of analogy in linguistics in today's era is that there is a variety of knowledge and skills about metaphor. During a person's life, he tries to liken something or event-phenomena on the basis of interdependence on something else or event-phenomena, and uses metaphors for this. In this way, the speaker achieves inking in his or her speech and delivering information to the listener in whole or in part.

The metaphor is originally an intrusive word from Greek, meaning "to move", "to move". This art is considered a kind of displacement of word meanings, and this type of fine art is based on the mutual similarity between things and phenomena. Basically, writers and poets make extensive use of the art of using (metaphor) in their works in a sense other than the word itself, that is, figuratively. The use of words and phrases in a portable sense, based on analogy, or their meaning in combinations of words and phrases, occurs on the basis of metaphor.

For example, "Sky fires decorated the night." This means: the shining of the stars at night is likened to the fiery fire in the sky. This was used as a decoration for the night.

Metaphor it is a figure of speech that refers to something else, mentioning something. In metaphors, there is a comparison of two things that are not so related

to each other, but whose general characteristics are similar to each other. Metaphor is a figure of speech, a rhetorical effect, which means one thing, directly mentioning another. There may be clarity between the two ideas, or hidden similarities can be identified. Metaphor is often compared to other means of artistic representation, such as metonymy, hyperbola, antithesis, and mimicry.

"All-world stage,
And all men and women are just players;
They have exits and entrances..."

William Shakespeare

In this passage, Shakespeare made good use of the art of metaphor, since here the word “world” is not actually a “scene” when we analyze it verbatim. Through these words, Shakespeare tries to fully deliver a dream about human beings and their behavior, their behavior. Using a comparison between the world and the stage, it influenced the listener and achieved an increase in the artistry of the work.

Metaphor often helps people to connect language with life and to understand language. To say that metaphor is an integral part of everyday communication between people, we are not mistaken at all. Its location within speech is not always identifiable.

In teaching such a vocabulary, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of what a metaphor is, and the standard definitions do not supply sufficient explanations.

Therefore, some of the dominant theories about metaphor are examined in order to extrapolate more precise concepts. This analysis leads to the conclusion that it is the multi-faceted duality of sense in a metaphor that distinguishes it from any other kind of expression, which cannot be fully appreciated unless both the pragmatic and the semantic aspects of metaphor are taken into account. Essentially, metaphor is the use of an expression to refer to something in a distinctly different conceptual, phenomenal, or experiential domain in order to imply that two things may be seen as if they were similar when in fact they are substantially different. The speaker and hearer tacitly agree to see this similarity, all the while holding in mind the fact that there is no actual similarity. Consequently, the expression used metaphorically is given not only two referents, but also a duality of sense: its literal and conventional

sense and the sense communicated by the metaphorical comparison; in Kittay's (1987) terms, a 'first-order' and a 'second-order' meaning.

The process of metaphoric extension should be included among those central patterns of word usage that are adding "new dimensions to our view of vocabulary" (Carter and McCarthy 1988, p. 201).

References

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